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“EUNVAILORIN”

(The Ever-Growing Vine of Wisdom)

The human mind, a restless, boundless sea,
Forever thirsting for the light of lore,
Like golden laughter, bright and ever-free,
It longs for wonders, yearning to explore.

The youth, the hope that nations dearly keep,
A key that opens doors to futures bright,
May wisdom guide them through the waters deep,
And grace their hearts with ever-burning light.

O may the torch of learning ever gleam,
A flame through the tempest and the shade,
The book's soft pages whisper forth a dream,
Where truth and wisdom never faint nor fade.

Like vines that weave through time in endless flow,
So knowledge blooms and hearts in wisdom grow.